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MODERN SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO FUTURE DOCTORS OF PHILOSOPHY TRAINING (EDUCATIONAL AND SCIENTIFIC PROGRAMM «GENERAL PEDAGOGY AND HISTORY OF PEDAGOGY»)

СУЧАСНІ НАУКОВІ ПІДХОДИ У ПІДГОТОВЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ ДОКТОРІВ ФІЛОСОФІЇ ЗА ОСВІТНЬО-НАУКОВОЮ ПРОГРАМОЮ «ЗАГАЛЬНА ПЕДАГОГІКА ТА ІСТОРІЯ ПЕДАГОГІКИ»

The purpose of the article is to determine and reveal modern scientific approaches in the course of doctors of philosophy training according to the educational and scientific «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» program based on the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical, historical and pedagogical works of the Ukrainian and foreign scientists.

Methodology. To implement the outlined purpose of the study, a set of general scientific methods was used: analysis and synthesis of philosophical, pedagogical, historical and pedagogical works of the Ukrainian and foreign scientists to ground scientific approaches in the training of the researchers of the historical and pedagogical process at the third (educational and scientific) level; systematization and generalization in order to understand the scientific context of the problem and present the results of the research.

Scientific novelty. The article analyzes the educational and scientific «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» program of training doctors of philosophy; modern scientific approaches (sociocultural, historiographical, source studies, systemic, paradigmatic, synergetic, hermeneutic, narrative, anthropological, personalistic, axiological), which are used to form the general and professional competencies of the future researchers in the field of general pedagogy and the history of pedagogy, have been characterized; the normative and selective educational components offered for mastery according to the specified educational and scientific program have been outlined.

Conclusions. The use of sociocultural, historiographical, source studies, systemic, paradigmatic, synergistic, hermeneutic, narrative, anthropological, personalistic and axiological approaches in the training of future specialists with the scientific degree «Doctor of Philosophy» will ensure the improvement of the research culture in the field of pedagogical sciences, the formation of methodological, scientific and professional and research competences, which is specified in the deepening of knowledge of the theoretical and methodological principles of pedagogy, the broadening of philosophical and cultural knowledge.

Keywords: doctors of philosophy training, educational and scientific program, scientific approach, pedagogy, history of pedagogy.

Мета статті – на основі аналізу філософських, педагогічних, історико-педагогічних праць українських і зарубіжних учених визначити та розкрити сучасні наукові підходи у підготовці докторів філософії за освітньо-науковою програмою «Загальна педагогіка та історія педагогіки».

Методи дослідження. Задля реалізації окресленої цілі дослідження використано комплекс загальнонаукових методів: аналіз і синтез філософських, педагогічних, історико-педагогічних праць українських і зарубіжних учених з метою обґрунтування наукових підходів у підготовці дослідників історико-педагогічного процесу на третьому (освітньо-науковому) рівні; систематизація та узагальнення задля розуміння наукового контексту проблеми та представлення результатів здійсненого дослідження.

Наукова новизна. У статті проаналізовано освітньо-наукову програму підготовки докторів філософії «Загальна педагогіка та історія педагогіки»; схарактеризовано сучасні наукові підходи (соціокультурний, історіографічний, джерелознавчий, системний, парадигмальний, синергетичний, герменевтичний, нарративний, антропологічний, персоналістичний, аксіологічний), що застосовуються для формування загальних і професійних компетентностей майбутніх дослідників у сфері загальної педагогіки та історії педагогіки; окреслено нормативні та вибіркові освітні компоненти, пропонувані для опанування за визначеною освітньо-науковою програмою.

Висновки. Застосування у підготовці майбутніх фахівців з науковим ступенем «Доктор філософії» соціокультурного, історіографічного, джерелознавчого, системного,

парадигмального, синергетичного, герменевтичного, наративного, антропологічного, персоналістичного та аксіологічного підходів забезпечить підвищення дослідницької культури у галузі педагогічних наук, формування методологічної, науково-професійної і дослідницької компетентностей, що конкретизується в поглибленні знань з теоретичних і методологічних основ педагогіки, розширенні філософсько-культурологічних знань.

Ключові слова: підготовка докторів філософії, освітньо-наукова програма, науковий підхід, педагогіка, історія педагогіки.

The problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. Ukraine's European development priorities require the modernization of the domestic education system, in particular those components that are related to the training of competent professionals for various spheres of society. This also applies to future doctors of philosophy – students of education of the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education. The Law of Ukraine «On Higher Education» (2014) states that the training of applicants at the third (educational and scientific) level of higher education involves the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, skills, abilities and other competencies sufficient to produce new ideas, solve complex problems in the field of professional and research-innovative activity, mastering the methodology of the scientific and pedagogical activity, as well as conducting one's own scientific research, the results of which have scientific novelty, theoretical and practical significance. In this regard, there is a need to update and improve scientific and methodological approaches in the formation of future doctors of philosophy of general and professional competencies necessary for research or to perform other functions and tasks. Therefore, modern models of training doctors of philosophy in the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» require understanding of scientific approaches.

The analysis of the basic researches and publications on the problem. The analysis of scientific works shows that the issue of training scientific and scientific-pedagogical staff of the highest qualification is the subject of scientific interest as Ukrainian (M. Biryukova, I. Kozubtsova, V. Lugovyi, A. Rachynsky, I. Regeylo, S. Sysoeva, O. Spirin, A. Yashin, etc.), and foreign scientists (Ph. Altbach, M. Nerad, E. Lin and others). In some publications of Ukrainian researcher, N. Hupan who is the history of education specialist, the specificity of formation of historical and pedagogical competence during

the training of doctors of philosophy is outlined (Hupan, 2002, 2013, 2019). At the same time, scientific approaches in the preparation of future researchers of the historical and pedagogical process because of the transformation processes in the system of higher education and historical and pedagogical science need to be defined and substantiated, which has become the subject of this scientific research.

The purpose of the article is to determine and reveal modern scientific approaches in the course of doctors of philosophy training according to the educational and scientific «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» program based on the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical, historical and pedagogical works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists.

The coverage of the procedure of theoretical and methodological research. To implement the outlined purpose of the study, a set of general scientific methods was used: analysis and synthesis of philosophical, pedagogical, historical and pedagogical works of Ukrainian and foreign scientists to ground scientific approaches in the training of the researchers of the historical and pedagogical process at the third (educational and scientific) level; systematization and generalization in order to understand the scientific context of the problem and present the results of the research.

The presentation of the basic material of the research with the obtained scientific results grounding. Provide training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical staff in the field of Education / Pedagogy, by acquiring competencies sufficient to perform original research, in particular in the field of general pedagogy, history of education and comparative pedagogy, the results of which have scientific novelty, theoretical and practical significance, and also their support during the preparation and defence of the dissertation, called the educational and scientific program «General pedagogy and history of pedagogy», which since 2019 is implemented at the T. H. Shevchenko National University

«Chernihiv Collegium». This program is based on scientific as well as scientific and pedagogical developments that take into account the current state of development of general pedagogy, history of education and comparative studies and research, which is an integral part of European standards of education (*Educational and Scientific Program*, 2019).

The range of research, according to the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy», relates to

- theoretical problems of pedagogy;
- socio-cultural determinants of modern education;
- methodology of pedagogical science;
- theoretical and methodological foundations of educational reform;
- globalization and their impact on educational system development;
- world trends in education and pedagogical science;
- methodological and general theoretical problems of historical and pedagogical research;
- source studies as a component of pedagogical research;
- development of national pedagogy, history of education in Ukraine in different historical periods;
- personalities in the historical and pedagogical discourse;
- comparative analysis of educational processes in foreign countries (*Educational and Scientific Program*, 2019).

The content of the educational and scientific program, following the Procedure for training graduates of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (2016) and the outlined fields and specialities, is focused on the development of research potential, set of general and professional competencies of future doctors of philosophy. The combination of teaching and research during the implementation of the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» is based on *the principles of*

- scientific creativity;
- openness;
- equality of rights;
- voluntariness;
- scientific collaboration;
- academic integrity (*Educational and Scientific Program*, 2019).

The main characteristic of such training is the orientation of the educational environment on the formation of the third (educational and scientific) level students the ability to apply knowledge to solve research and practical problems.

Acquisition of competencies defined by the educational-scientific program «General

pedagogy and history of pedagogy» is provided by the *disciplines of compulsory and elective cycles*. The list of *compulsory* includes the following educational components:

- «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication»;
- «Pedagogical and organizational culture of freelancers and research institutions»;
- «Modern theories of cognition»;
- «Pedagogical practice»;
- «Research practice»;
- «Methodology and methods of scientific research»;
- «Organization of research work and project management»;
- «Regulatory framework of scientific and scientific-pedagogical activity»;
- «World system of grant support and commercialization of scientific research»;
- «Modern information technologies in scientific research»;
- «Ukrainian scientific language in scientific and pedagogical communication» (*Curriculum*, 2019).

The formation of an individual educational trajectory is due to the *free choice* of disciplines of the sample *elective cycle*. Taking into account the specifics of postgraduate research, they are offered a list of such educational components, namely:

- «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science»;
- «Theory of general and comparative pedagogy»;
- «Transformational processes in pedagogy XX – early XXI century»;
- «Actual problems of general and comparative pedagogy»;
- «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research»;
- «Methodology of comparative and pedagogical research»;
- «Organization and implementation of historical and pedagogical research»;
- «Organization and implementation of comparative and pedagogical research»;
- «Historiography of the history of pedagogy»;
- «Historiography of general and comparative pedagogy»;
- «Historical and pedagogical source studies»;
- «Information support of scientific research in general and comparative pedagogy» (*Curriculum*, 2019).

The curriculum of the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» is 60 credits for the entire period of study, which the graduate student is expected to complete during the first three years. This is to ensure that the last year

of study of the third (educational and scientific) level is devoted exclusively to the preparation of the dissertation for defence (*Curriculum*, 2019).

We should stress, that the formation of a new generation of doctors of philosophy requires updating scientific approaches in their training. We consider a scientific approach in pedagogy as an asset of learning conceptual ideas and basic principles from the standpoint of which the pedagogical object, phenomenon, process are analyzed. Characteristics of scientific approaches are a component of research methodology in the field of analytical and theoretical research on the history of pedagogy and general pedagogy. As the well-known Ukrainian researcher L. Berezivska (2010) notes, «the subject of historical and pedagogical research, as a rule, combines the processes that underlie the study of such scientific disciplines as the history of pedagogy, pedagogy, history of Ukraine, the political history of Ukraine, philosophy» (p. 37). This necessitates the selection of disciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches to research. It is worthy to underline, that this also applies to the subject of general pedagogical research. Therefore, the formation of future doctors of philosophy of historical and pedagogical and general pedagogical competencies requires the use of several interdisciplinary different approaches. We understand the term interdisciplinary approaches as those used in various sciences and aimed at multicultural knowledge of the studied objects, processes, phenomena, while disciplinary approaches are applied in particular science and characterize the phenomena studied by this science. Since the training of future doctors of philosophy in the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» has significant specifics, primarily related to its complex, interdisciplinary nature and content, forms and methods of teaching, the application of these scientific approaches requires some clarification. In particular, it is advisable to rely on some approaches from the relevant branches of the humanities, which are most consistent with this educational program and contribute to the realization of its goals and objectives. Among the many methodological approaches in the training of future doctors of philosophy to form their professional competencies, we choose

- the sociocultural;
- the historiographical;
- the source study;
- the systemic;
- the paradigmatic;
- the synergetic;
- the hermeneutic;

- the narrative;
- the anthropological;
- the personalistic;
- the axiological approaches.

Let's dwell in more detail on their characteristics. The significance of *the sociocultural approach* (Boguslavsky, 1999; Sukhomlynska, 2003) in the training of future doctors of philosophy lies in the formation of their understanding that pedagogical processes in any of the historical epochs are always determined by the general state of society and culture, as the content of education and upbringing depends on the state interests and the specifics of socio-political life. «Educational space», says the famous Ukrainian researcher O. Sukhomlynska (2003), «is mostly in the social sphere, reflects social, political, legal, economic and ideological processes. Together with pedagogical processes, they set the parameters of school policy and the functioning of education» (p. 48). The application of the socio-cultural approach contributes to the formation of students' ability to analyze pedagogical phenomena and facts in the context of the development of a particular state and society. It is provided, first of all, because the structure of the curriculum for training specialists in the educational-scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» involves the study of general and professional disciplines that highlight the relationship of social processes and education, their interactions and interdependence. In particular, this applies to the following disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization of research and project management», «Regulatory framework of scientific and scientific-pedagogical activities», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Actual problems of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy».

Recently, the attention of comparativists and historians of pedagogy has increased to the use of *the historiographical* and *the source-based approaches* in research as methodological tools (Berezivska, 2017, 2018; Caspard, 2014; Depaepe, 2009; Dichek, 2014; Freeman, 2017; Havrylenko, 2021; Hupan, 2002, 2013, 2019; Kelly, 2014; Sukhomlynska, 1999, etc.). The historiographical approach allows to identify «unexplored or little-studied scientific problems, to concentrate research efforts around them, to ensure the relevance and theoretical significance» of historical and pedagogical intelligence and at the same time is a «manifestation of the researcher's culture» (Berezivska, 2018, p. 4). Substantiation of future doctors of philosophy training taking

into account *the historiographical approach* will promote the formation of their skills to identify the state of the problem of pedagogical science, educational processes in Ukraine and abroad in pedagogical comparative studies and historical and pedagogical science; to systematize and analyze historical-pedagogical, historical, historiosophical works, in which the problems of education, training, the upbringing of children and adults are covered from different methodological positions; to formulate conclusions about the tendencies of studying the studied phenomenon and to outline the range of tasks of scientific research.

The application of *the source study approach*, which consists in «the probability of reproduction pedagogical reality of the past by the historian of pedagogy, the ability to organize a cognitive dialogue between present and past, understanding the results» (Berezivska, 2017, p. 6). It focuses on the formation of «General pedagogy and history of pedagogy» graduate students, several research skills: to identify, systematize and analyze different types of sources, which cover educational processes; compare a set of available sources; evaluate events and processes of the past and present. The implementation of *historiographical and source studies approaches* in the preparation of doctors of philosophy is provided by the educational components «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historiography of general and comparative pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Information support of research on general and comparative pedagogy».

An important descriptive tool and prescriptive methodological guideline in research on general pedagogy, history of education and pedagogical comparative studies is *the systematic approach*. It was founded in the 60's-early 70's of the twentieth century. and began to develop rapidly by representatives of philosophical and pedagogical sciences (Blauberg, 1997; Bondar, 2017; Kushnir, 2001, etc.). The systematic approach is one of the most recognized and well-known forms of interdisciplinary, general scientific knowledge related to the research, design and construction of objects as systems. At the heart of the content of the system approach is philosophical general methodological knowledge, in particular the principle of systematicity, which forms a special «epistemological prism or a special dimension of reality» (Blauberg, 1997, p. 312). According to the Ukrainian scientist V. Bondar (2017), a systematic approach helps to reveal the structure of «studied processes and phenomena», to determine the internal factors

and external conditions that affect the functioning of the studied system (p. 87). Because of the above, the application of a systematic approach in the training of future doctors of philosophy will contribute to the formation of their ability to organize existing knowledge about the phenomenon, summarize the results of scientific research to create a holistic picture of educational processes in Ukraine and abroad in different historical periods.

The training of graduate students in the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» is based on *the paradigmatic approach*. It was introduced in pedagogical science in the 1990s by Russian researchers M. Boguslavsky, B. Gershunsky, and G. Kornetov, and developed in the works of Ukrainian scientists L. Berezivska (2009), N. Lavrychenko (2018) and O. Sukhomlynska (1999) and others. The paradigmatic approach, as defined by O. Sukhomlynska (1999), «is the genesis of theoretical positions that allow scientists and practitioners to identify, formulate and describe holistic models of education, ie the internal logic of the subject as a system of binary oppositions» (p. 45). The application of this approach allows future scientific and scientific-pedagogical workers to trace the change of educational paradigms in the period under study and their impact on the education system, to compare them with previous and subsequent educational paradigms; comprehend the transformation of goals, objectives, values, principles, organization of education, its content, methods, tools and forms of organization of learning, control and evaluation of learning outcomes in different historical periods.

The training of doctors of philosophy in the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy» is based on *the synergetic approach* (Boguslavsky, 1999; Kagan, 2005; Kremen, 2012;). Synergetics is based on the fact that new scientific ideas, concepts, hypotheses are generated not only by new (in our case, pedagogical) facts but also by various nonlinear connections between theories (Boguslavsky, 2005, p. 37). Taking into account the synergetic approach is important in the training of future doctors of philosophy, as it helps to identify undisclosed or insufficiently disclosed processes that were a hidden layer of historical and pedagogical phenomena (Sukhomlynska, 2003, p. 45).

The application of a synergetic approach in the training of future doctors of philosophy is relevant since scientific developments on education and upbringing have accumulated a large number of facts and materials that cannot

be explained from the standpoint of the individual, traditional methods adopted in pedagogy and other humanities and social sciences. Their analysis requires a different conceptualization, liberation from the stereotypes of the past, the transition to a synergistic (interdisciplinary) methodology (Kremen, 2012, p. 127).

The argument in the use of a synergetic approach in the formation of research competencies of young scientists is the statement of M. Boguslavsky that the synergetic worldview has the following essential features:

1. The genesis of the pedagogical worldview has its internal logic, which does not coincide (but resonates in a way) with external determinants (Boguslavsky, 1999, p. 37).

2. Polyphonic processes that are the object of knowledge (their alternative, variability). With a synergetic approach, science is mostly interested not only in the external, visible layer of the historical and pedagogical process but also in what lies beneath it. Under such conditions, there is a revival of their human, moral content, that is a return to the humanistic origins of historical and pedagogical knowledge, the focus on key issues is combined with the impact on the macrosystem of small pedagogical processes (Boguslavsky, 1999, p. 37).

3. In the synergetic approach, it is especially important to identify and demonstrate the influence of individual figures in education and science on the system, which is in a state of instability, which causes macro-changes (Boguslavsky, 1999, p. 38).

Implementation of the synergetic approach is provided in the process of studying such disciplines of the curriculum as «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research». works of teachers-scientists and historical-pedagogical documents, to reveal in them the hidden context influencing objectivity of pedagogical discourse.

For future researchers in the field of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy, it is extremely important to understand, master and use in practice *the hermeneutic approach* (Gadamer, 1988; Reeker, 1995; Sukhomlinska, 2003, 2005), which is used in the process of interpreting texts, in particular historical ones, which reflect both the research subject and the social context of the outlined period, so it is especially relevant when developing the source base of each study.

According to P. Reeker (1995), interpretation prolongs the life of historical sources, because written historical sources are «not a closed package, which, without opening, is passed from hand to hand, but a treasure from which you can draw a handful and which is replenished in this process. Every tradition lives on through interpretation; it is at this price that it continues, that is, it remains a living tradition» (Reeker, 1995, p. 38).

The hermeneutic approach in the training of doctors of philosophy will allow them in the future to achieve not only an adequate understanding and interpretation the form and content of sources but also the circumstances that gave them a rise, the meaning contained in them, the consequences of their appearance (Dichek, 2015, p. 91–92).

The practical task of historical hermeneutics in the training of future researchers in the field of history of pedagogy is to establish the content of concepts, terms, language turns that have gone out of circulation or acquired a different meaning. It should also reveal the content of historical events and phenomena that are incomprehensible to modern man, as well as reveal the hidden meaning of the historical source. To do this, the source is perceived as an element of a particular culture, considered in connection with the specific historical conditions of its origin (Vorovka, 2019, p. 27). Therefore, an important feature of the hermeneutic approach and its application in the training of future doctors of philosophy is the attempt to understand not only the content of the processed documents but also the position and views of their authors caused by certain circumstances related to socio-political conditions of society.

According to the hermeneutic theory of interpretation of texts, the interpretation of historical documents used in research, especially unpublished, should be carried out in such a way as to convey their substantive content exactly as it is laid down in the text, regardless of internal contexts.

The hermeneutic approach is used in the process of studying «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization and implementation of historical and pedagogical research», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy» and «Historical and pedagogical source studies», when in practical classes and during independent work education analyzes historical and pedagogical documents and works of teachers that belong to different historical periods and are related to different socio-cultural contexts.

Unlike source studies approach (including with the help of hermeneutic tools),

the subject of which is «witnesses of time» – sources that necessarily belong to the period under consideration, the historiographical analysis examines historical narratives that contain the author's interpretation of historical and pedagogical events. The historical and pedagogical narrative is a historiographical text that contains a picture of the historical past constructed by a historian using the source information obtained and interpreted by him (Vorovka, 2019, pp. 42, 49). O. Sukhomlynska (2005) draws attention to this, emphasizing that any exposition of historical and pedagogical research has the form of a narrative, regardless of the problem posed (p. 45). Therefore, *the narrative approach* should be used to form the ability of future doctors of philosophy to analyze the historiographical basis of the study.

The narrative characterizes historical and pedagogical events and phenomena not as conditioned by the objective regularity of the historical process, but as those that arise in the context of the narrative of events and phenomena and are inherently related to interpretation. According to this understanding, history, says researcher L. Vakhovsky (2007), is not what was really in the past, but what we tell about the past – a story about the past (p. 43). The use of the narrative approach during practical classes in the disciplines «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization and implementation of historical and pedagogical research» and «Historiography of the history of pedagogy» allows future doctors of philosophy to focus on how and in what conditions events that exactly and in what way various socio-cultural, political-economic, historical-pedagogical and other factors could affect the views and beliefs of the scientist. All this becomes essential for the analysis and conclusion about the content of the work they are studying.

Application of *the anthropological approach* (Boguslavsky, 1999; Kremen, 2009; Ushinsky, 1983) provides formation at future doctors of philosophy of understanding of anthropocentrism of historical-pedagogical and modern educational processes in which the person, the personality is a subject of social and pedagogical reality. According to K. Ushinsky (1983), the anthropological approach meant the integration of data from all human sciences (psychology, anatomy, physiology, logic, philosophy, geography, history, ethnography) and their use in the organization and implementation of the pedagogical process. Through the prism of the anthropological approach in the preparation of students of the third (educational and scientific level)

conditions are created for their implementation in future professional scientific and pedagogical activities of child-centred and student-centric scientific concepts.

The guiding principle of anthropological theories, in particular the pedagogical anthropology of K. Ushinsky (1983), the philosophy of anthropology of V. Kremen (2009) and other theories, is anthropocentrism, which puts man at the centre of research, stimulates the study of the history of pedagogy in the human dimension. This way highlights the specifics of the development of socio-cultural processes in a given society. According to V. Kremen (2009), «anthropocentrism is the actualization of humanistic tendencies in the modern era, a departure from rationalized pragmatic imperatives» (p. 15).

The application of the principle of anthropocentrism «develops and cultivates a reflective, polyphonic type of cognition that overcomes the economocentrism (pragmaticism) of human existence» (Kremen, 2009, p. 16).

The anthropological approach modernizes the research tools of historical and pedagogical research, as during classes the attention of students is focused on the analysis of teachers' contribution to the development of pedagogical phenomena and construction of pedagogical technologies, study and understanding of requests and interests of participants in different sociocultural contexts. It is implemented during the study of such disciplines of the curriculum as «Modern theories of knowledge», «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Actual problems of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy».

Among the scientific approaches that should be relied on in the process of training future doctors of philosophy with the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy», we outline a personalistic approach (Dichek, 2001; Hupan, 2013; Stern, 1998; Sukhomlynska, 2003), because «pedagogical personality represents the work of a teacher as an individual creator, but above all as an expression of thought and practice of his era» (Sukhomlynska, 2003, p. 37). The application of *the personalistic approach* means coverage during lectures and practical classes in some disciplines of the curriculum, such as «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Current issues of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy», «Historiography of history pedagogy «and» Historical and pedagogical

source studies «, the scientist’s contribution to the development of pedagogical science and practice. The personalistic approach demonstrates the connection of scientific knowledge with the personality of a scientist or teacher-practitioner, his life and work, which contributes to the revival of humanistic traditions of historical and pedagogical research and allows to realize that history is made by individuals, and the process of formation of younger generations and the interaction of these prominent figures (Dichek, 2001, p. 19).

The reliance on a personalistic approach describes pedagogical reality in time and space and coverage of the problem in a broad historical context (Yanchenko, 2017, p. 32), has a positive impact on the humanization of historical and pedagogical process and research in education and pedagogy. Therefore, it contributes to the modernization of the content of training future doctors of philosophy.

Important in the formation of a new generation of researchers, in our opinion, is *the axiological approach* (Havrylenko, 2019), based on the works of leading Ukrainian scientists in the field of education and pedagogy, namely: I. Bekh (2007),

O. Savchenko (2009), I. Zyazyun (2008) and others. Borrowed from the philosophical discipline of axiology, which studies values as the basis of human existence and as a basis that directs and motivates human activity, its actions (Lavrychenko, 2018, p. 26), this approach provides an opportunity for the third (educational) level to identify pedagogical ideas about the values of education; to reveal the role of education in a system of values in children and adults formation; to trace the transformation of value orientations in different societies. The axiological approach runs through all the educational components of the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy».

In addition to the above, since the researches on the history of pedagogy, general pedagogy and teaching didactics are usually interdisciplinary by nature, they occur at the intersection of different disciplines (philosophy, pedagogy, linguistics, culture studies, history, sociology, psychology and natural sciences) (Persukova, 2016), future professionals need to be trained to integrate the above-mentioned approaches. The results of the study are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Modern scientific approaches in the training of future doctors of philosophy under the educational-scientific program «General pedagogy and history of pedagogy»

Approach, its character	It is aimed	Peculiarities of application (Realization)
Sociocultural, disciplinary	To form students’ understanding of pedagogical processes connection with historical epoch they are taking place, and the determination of the content of education and upbringing by the general state of society and culture; contributes to the formation of students’ ability to analyze pedagogical phenomena and facts in the context of the development of a particular state and society	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization of research and project management», «Regulatory framework of scientific and scientific-pedagogical activities», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Actual problems of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy»
Historiographical, disciplinary	To identify unexplored or little-studied scientific problems, to concentrate research efforts, to ensure the relevance and theoretical significance of educational processes in Ukraine and abroad	The study of disciplines: «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historiography of general and comparative pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Information support of research on general and comparative pedagogy»
Source study, disciplinary	To form students’ research skills to identify, systematize and analyze different types of sources, which cover educational processes; to compare a set of available sources; to evaluate events and processes of the past and present	The study of disciplines: «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historiography of general and comparative pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Information support of research on general and comparative pedagogy»

Approach, its character	It is aimed	Peculiarities of application (Realization)
Systemic, interdisciplinary	To form students' ability to organize existing knowledge about the educational phenomenon, to summarize the results of scientific research to create a holistic picture of educational processes in Ukraine and abroad in different historical periods	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization of research and project management», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research».
Paradigmatic, interdisciplinary	To form students' ability to trace the change of educational paradigms in the period under study and their impact on the education system; to compare previous and subsequent educational paradigms; to comprehend the transformation of goals, objectives, values, principles, organization of education, content, methods, tools and forms of organization of learning, to control and evaluate the learning outcomes in different historical periods	The study of disciplines: «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Actual problems of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy».
Synergetic, interdisciplinary	To identify undisclosed or insufficiently disclosed processes that were a hidden layer of historical and pedagogical phenomena; to demonstrate the influence of individual figures in education and science on the system; to reveal in documents the hidden context influencing objectivity of pedagogical discourse	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy», «Historical and pedagogical source studies», «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research». works of teachers-scientists and historical-pedagogical documents
Hermeneutic, disciplinary	To understand the content of the documents, and the position and views of their authors caused by certain circumstances related to socio-political conditions of society	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization and implementation of historical and pedagogical research», «Historiography of the history of pedagogy» and «Historical and pedagogical source studies»
Narrative, disciplinary	To form the students' ability to analyze the historiographical basis of the study;	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Organization and implementation of historical and pedagogical research» and «Historiography of the history of pedagogy»
Anthropological, interdisciplinary	To develops students' reflective, polyphonic type of cognition that overcomes the pragmacentrism	The study of disciplines: «Modern theories of knowledge», «Methodology of historical and pedagogical research», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Actual problems of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy»
Personalistic, disciplinary	To demonstrate the connection of scientific knowledge with the personality of a scientist or teacher-practitioner, to contribute to the revival of humanistic traditions of historical and pedagogical research; to allows to realize that history is made by individuals	The study of disciplines: «Foreign language in scientific and pedagogical communication», «Theory of the history of education and pedagogical science», «Current issues of general pedagogy and history of pedagogy», «Historiography of history pedagogy «and» Historical and pedagogical source studies «
Axiological,	provides an opportunity for the third	all the educational components of the

Approach, its character	It is aimed	Peculiarities of application (Realization)
disciplinary	(educational) level to identify pedagogical ideas about the values of education; to reveal the role of education in a system of values in children and adult's formation; to trace the transformation of value orientations in different societies	educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy»

The description of the basic material of the research with the obtained scientific results grounding. On this basis, we conclude that the use in the training of future specialists with the degree of «Doctor of Philosophy» sociocultural, historiographical, source studies, systemic, paradigmatic, synergetic, hermeneutics, narrative, anthropological, personalistic and axiological approaches will increase scientific formation in the field of pedagogical sciences professional and research competencies, which is specified in the deepening of knowledge of the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogy, the expansion of philosophical and cultural knowledge needed by future educators, teachers and scientists. The formation of such competencies, based on the

latest methodological and theoretical knowledge, allows young scientists to develop pedagogical reality following European guidelines for the development of Ukrainian education and new social needs, participate in the formation of modern scientific and information space, create scientific products based on theoretical and methodological changes occurring in domestic education and line with global trends.

Prospects for future research, the subject of which is the training of future doctors of philosophy in the educational and scientific program «General Pedagogy and History of Pedagogy», are to substantiate and develop practical aspects of the educational process and research work of students.

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